

Evaluation of the Customer Satisfaction of the Courier Companies using the SERVQUAL Model: Basis for Client Action Plan

Author's Details: Dr. Fhrizz S. De Jesus¹, Prof. Winnie C. Villanueva²

¹Faculty, Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, Atate Campus, Palayan City, Philippines

²Faculty, Central Luzon State University, Science City of Munoz, Philippines

Abstract

The topic of distribution for the Courier's firm will be discussed in this study. The Evaluation of the Customer Satisfaction of the Courier Companies using the SERVQUAL Model: was assessed using descriptive analysis in this study. To collect research data, a survey was performed, which will be done utilizing the approach. Individual consumers who had problems using the courier distribution to order items through the Internet/online received questionnaires. Due to the global pandemic, this study was done over the internet in General Mamerto Natividad, Nueva Ecija. From August to September 2021, the researchers acquired all of the data. This study provides, analyzes, and evaluates all of the data collected in textual and tabular forms in order to address the study's concerns. According to the gathered data most of the respondents considered courier services that acknowledge regular customer were critical to business success. The findings of the SERVQUAL study indicate a notable degree of concern given to customers near transaction point, having personnel with clean and neat appearance affect the image of the courier company. The findings and outcomes of this study may have important implications for profitability, attracting new customers, and analyzing client preferences through the usage of the SERVQUAL MODEL.

Keywords: Courier Service Company, SERVQUAL MODEL, Customer Satisfactions, Action Client Plan

INTRODUCTION

It is imperative that online delivery services be made available during this pandemic. As more and more people choose to stay at home, they are increasingly turning away from traditional shopping and toward online shopping, increasing the demand for courier services. The term "courier service" refers to a service that picks up and delivers items or papers from one location to another. It could be local or international in nature. A courier company is a company that provides such delivery services. According to Diaz (2019), it is important that the company meet the demand of the customers, especially on the quality of service. Customers are the heart of the business. They are the foundation, the key element for success and the end user of the product/service. Their loyalty to the business brings feedback to the provider and leaves a positive impact especially if the company fulfills their demand and need.

Yadav et. al (2015) stated that satisfaction refers to the extent which customers are satisfied with the products and services provided by a business. Customer satisfaction is important because when a customer is happy with a service or goods provider, they are most likely to be loyal and to make repeat orders. Furthermore Diaz (2019) stated some studies show that a very satisfied customer is nearly six times more likely to be loyal and to repurchase and/or recommend a product than to a customer who is just satisfied. Moreover, the significant increase in loyalty can increase more or less half of the company's profit.

Service quality can be measured by means of the SERVQUAL model (Wiid et. al 2015). Owusu-Frimpong & Nwankwo (2012) stated that, in spite of the widespread usage of the SERVQUAL model, there have been numerous criticisms on theoretical and procedural bases, however, the SERVQUAL model still maintains a powerful diagnostic authority and remains a convincing measurement of service quality. In addition, Wiid et. al (2015) also stated that the SERVQUAL model evaluates customer satisfaction based on the service quality dimensions which are questions based on the perceptions and expectations of customers, and the difference in answers is an indication of customer satisfaction.

In order to provide better and faster service from one site to another, technology has been employed for a long period of time. Using courier services to transport stuff makes it easier and faster to get things done on

time. Long-distance travel is avoided, saving people the hassles of getting there. There is a tremendous impact on the rest of the globe from this area of the economy. The goal of this research is to assess courier companies' customer satisfaction using the SERVQUAL model. The significance of this research is to provide solutions to potential problems that courier companies may face.

This study aimed to evaluate the Customer Satisfaction of the Courier using the SERVQUAL Model. It also identifies their Problems and provide Recommendations. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following:

1. How may the profile of the respondents be analyzed in terms of:

1.1 Age;

1.2 Sex;

1.3 Monthly Income; and

1.4 Average Monthly Parcel Orders?

2. How may the Customer Satisfaction of the Courier Companies be evaluated using the SERVQUAL model in terms of:

2.1 Reliability;

2.2 Responsiveness;

2.3 Competence;

2.4 Access;

2.5 Courtesy;

2.6 Communication;

2.7 Credibility;

2.8 Security;

2.9 Knowing the customer; and

2.10 Tangibles?

3. What Client Action plan may be proposed to improve the client satisfaction to the customers.

Customer Satisfaction

A service provider's ultimate goal is to ensure that their customers are completely satisfied with their service. When a customer's needs and expectations are met, he or she will feel satisfied. Customers' perception of the level of service they received in comparison to what they expected is referred to as their satisfaction. According to an article titled "What is Customer Satisfaction" when a customer receives a service, their personal interpretation of whether the service was satisfactory or unacceptable is called perception. Customer satisfaction evaluates the degree of satisfaction of customers with the company's products, services, and functionality. Information on customer satisfaction can be obtained through surveys and ratings, which can help companies decide on how to improve or modify their products and services.

Ghoumrassi et. al (2017) stated that customer satisfaction gives marketers and businessmen a metric that they can use to manage and improve their businesses. It is a way to determine the continuity of the business or the continuation of a product's life by measuring the loyalty of the customers. If the customers are satisfied with

the performances, the continuity of businesses will not be a problem for most organizations. Nowadays, customer satisfaction has many aspects and it's not just linked to the quality and the costs of the product but also with the relationship of the service quality of logistics. Furthermore, Hong et. al (2019) also stated that Customer satisfaction refers to their evaluation of products or services based on the expected quality and perceived quality of the products or services, when customers are satisfied with the offerings, they tend to bring more profits to the organization either by doing repeat purchases or recommend them to others.

Customer satisfaction is a critical component of the business approach that defines the service's efficiency. It has been given a few concepts that may be used in many situations and are always associated with both items and services. It was defined as a product or service evaluation by the customer to determine whether the product or service meets the customer's wants and expectations. In addition, Ok et. al (2018) stated that customer satisfaction can determine how a company operates or provides goods or services; thus, customer satisfaction is the degree of achievement for all organizations, including the public sectors .

Service Quality and SERVQUAL Model

Sureshchandar, Rajendran & Anantharaman (2002) stated that service delivery organizations can gain a successful competitive edge over competitors through good service quality. However, a good administration that focuses on well trained staff, valuable program offering and its influence on customers, are also components of quality dimensions (Naidoo, 2011). Improving service quality should be a constant goal for courier service providers, and they should never stop being more proactive with client satisfaction by providing better and better courier services. According to Hong et. al (2019) Service quality plays an essential part in e-commerce platforms and logistics industries. Service quality has been widely discussed in the literature, and it is frequently seen as a function of customers' expectations of the benefit to be provided against their identification of the true value received. In a nutshell, benefit quality is the customer's overall reaction to the respective organization's benefit. In addition, Badruln et. al (2012) stated that service quality is the discrepancy between the customers' perceptions of a service offered by a business and the customers' expectations of that business offering that particular service. Service quality can be characterized as the capacity of a company to determine customers' desires effectively and to convey the service at a quality level that will at any time meet the customers' expectations (Brink & Berndt, 2009).

According to Jamal et. al (2018) one of the most well-known measures of service quality is the SERVQUAL, which is widely used in marketing and also in the service industry. The retail area was the main focus on the early investigations of service quality, where ten components were proposed to determine the general impression of service quality. They are reliability, responsiveness, competence, access, courtesy, communications, credibility, security, understanding customer, and tangibles. Pena et al.(2013) stated that SERVQUAL model has been proven an efficient tool for assessing the perceptions and expectations among users with regard to service quality. It is a worldwide recognized and used instrument for measuring service quality. According to Saliba et. al (2018), SERVQUAL is a research instrument that measures customers' perception of service quality and their expectation of the service. It then measures the difference between the expectation and perception to see if the perception is higher or lower than the expected. When it is lower, improvements need to be conducted in that quality dimension. Johnson et. al (2018) stated that the SERVQUAL scale is the most accurate method of measuring customer's satisfaction of a firm's service quality, and with minor adjustments it can be applied in different contexts.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Research Design

The study used the descriptive- evaluative method to assess the Courier Companies in General Mamerto Natividad City using the SERVQUAL MODEL and to develop a new Client Action plan to improve the client

satisfaction of the customers based on the results of the study. This design was used to carefully appraise the worthiness of this study.

In this study, the questionnaire instrument was utilized to collect the information needed. The research instrument helped the researchers to keep track of the evaluation in order to validate the information gathered. Furthermore, the researchers also had conducted series of interviews to validate the answers of the respondents

Research Locale

This research was conducted in General Mamerto Natividad where the respondents were identified. The list of the consumers of courier's services in Natividad, Nueva Ecija Profile were extracted from Phil Atlas website. The respondents of this study came from the different barangays found in Natividad of Nueva Ecija.

Respondents of the Study

The courier's company consumers are the target respondents in this study. The table below shows the distribution of respondents based on where they were found in the sample population.

Table 1. Distribution of the respondents per Brgy. General Mamerto Natividad Nueva Ecija.

Respondents	Population	Sample population
Courier's Company consumers	510	220

Table 1 shows the overall population, as well as the total number of respondents required to complete this survey in order to calculate the number of customers who receive packages, letters, and other mail. The entire sample population was estimated as 220 total number of consumers over 510 population of consumers in General Mamerto Natividad, using contemporary statistical techniques Raosoft.

Sample and Sampling Procedure

Purposive sampling was employed in this investigation. The total sample size of the respondents of this study are 220, from the total population of 510. This study uses Raosoft application to determine the sample size with 95% confidence level and 5% error of margin.

Raosoft Interform is a web survey and form application developer that allows you to construct sophisticated questionnaires with extended logic statements, as well as very big web questionnaires with enormous populations and/or large question sets (Raosoft, 2011). Purposive sampling was employed in this investigation a purposive sample is one that a researchers chooses based on their understanding of the topic and population. The participants are chosen depending on the sample's purpose, as indicated by the name.

Research Instrument

The research instruments used were the survey method, questionnaire. The distribution of questionnaire was online assessment by the researchers which is consisted of three parts, namely:

Part I. It consisted of the socio-demographic profile of the Couriers customer. The instrument used was checklist and filled out by the respondents.

Part II contained the assessment of Courier's Company distribution problem. It is composed of SERVQUAL Model. This part of the instrument was formulated in the modified 4-point Likert-scale (Strongly Disagree (4); Disagree (3); Agree (2); and Strongly Agree (1). Everything was entirely based and adapted from the questionnaire of Parasuman et. al (1985) entitled "A Conceptual Model of Service Quality and its Implication for Future Research (SERVQUAL)

Data Gathering Procedure

After the approval of the research topic entitled “**Evaluation of the Customer Satisfaction of the Courier Companies using the SERVQUAL Model: Problems and Recommendations**”, the researchers proceeded to the gathering of data and information from related researches, articles, and internet. The questionnaire was formulated through the gathered information and was checked by the researchers’ mentors. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was tested and measured with a score of .884, which means that the instrument has a good internal consistency. The validity of the research instrument was established by presenting the developed research instrument for the comments of the experts who rated the instrument with 4.80 as its weighted mean having a verbal interpretation of “very good”.

Before the distribution of the questionnaire, the researcher got an approval from the Courier Companies, through the request letters signed by the researchers, by his adviser, and approved by the Dean. After the distribution, the answered questionnaires were retrieved and the data were tallied for interpretation.

Data Analysis Techniques

The information gathered in the area was encoded, counted, and evaluated. The data was analyzed using statistical methods such as percentage, frequency distribution, and weighted mean, The following scales were used to interpret the data collected.

Table 2. Scales used for interpretation

Point	Scale Range	Explanation
1	1.00 – 0.99	Strongly Disagree
2	1.99 – 1.00	Disagree
3	2.99 – 2.00	Agree
4	4.00 – 3.00	Strongly Agree

Table 2 shows the scale used by the researchers in interpretation and description of data. To assess the frequency of the Courier’s Company distribution problem using 4 point Likert-scale. The aim of the researchers is to identify which of the Courier’s Company operations affects the performance of the distribution.

1. To describe the classification of the respondents, the researchers used the **weighted mean, frequency and percentage** to determine the number of respondents who answered a specific description pertaining to the respondents

2. In the evaluation of the respondents in Courier’s Company distribution problem ,the researchers employed **weighted mean and ranking** to determine the number of respondents who answered a specific description pertaining to the respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Table 1 to 4 shows the socio-demographic profile of the respondents.

1.1 Gender

Table 1. shows the gender profile of the respondents in terms of the Gender of the Respondents.

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	120	51 %
Male	100	49 %
Total	220	100%

In Table 1, women outnumber men by a margin of 51 percent to 49 percent, indicating that females prefer to shop online and use a courier service as a convenience rather than a necessity. According to the majority of respondents, they use courier services because they want to communicate with as few people as

possible while also making their lives easier by allowing them to place orders or fulfill other desires from home while being safe.

In an article entitled “ Women like online shopping more than men (2018)” stated that when it comes to ecommerce and online shopping it's women who are enthusiastic as male consumers tend to prefer shopping in brick-and-mortar retail locations. In addition, According to Escarpment (2017), courier service are convenient for both the sender and the receiver. The providers can quickly pick the item at your doorstep and deliver it directly to the intended receiver. It saves you the struggle to go out looking for appropriate options to send parcels. Same way, it saves the receiver the hassle of accessing the items as they can be dropped off at their physical addresses.

1.2 Age

Table 2 shows the Age Profile of the **respondents** in terms of the **Age of the respondents**.

Age	Frequency	Percentage
12 to 18 years old	70	31%
18 to 30 years old	101	55%
31 to 40 years old	29	8%
41 to 50 years old	19	5%
51 years old and above	1	1%
Total	220	100%

According to Table 2 the majority of respondents (55 percent) were between the ages of 18 and 30. This age group depicts a moment when individuals have too much information and are glued to their cellphones. This age group has a variety of desires, which are reflected in their purchase behavior, resulting in purchases from online stores and various platforms to fulfill their desires. According to the majority of respondents, individuals achieve their needs and desires through online shopping apps as well as the services of courier company now accessible on the mmarket

Smith (2015) stated that, Millennials, those consumers aged 18 to 34, remain the key age demographic for online commerce, spending more money online in a given year than any other age group. These consumers spend around \$2,000 annually on e-commerce, despite having lower incomes than older adults. According to the study internet usage and online shopping are most common in the university age 18-30 years old students even though they do not have sufficient funds for shopping but the university students found on the to listed using internet and has great intention towards online shopping (Edmunds et al., 2010).

1.3 Monthly Income

Table 3 shows the Financial Profile of the **respondents** in terms of the **Monthly Income**.

Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
5,000 Php and below	85	51%
5,001 Php to 10,000 Php	51	25%
10,001 Php to 20,000 Php	29	8%
20,001 Php to 30,000 Php	34	9%
30,001 Php to 40,000 Php	10	3%
40,001 Php to 50,000 Php	10	3%
Above 50,001 Php	1	1%
Total	220	100%

The vast majority of respondents earn 5,000 pesos per month, according to the statistics in the preceding table. This form of monthly income is generally linked with those who work part-time and currently attending school. These people focus on their desires and place purchases from online shopping websites as well as meal orders via the internet from the help of courier service. The majority of respondents say they are enticed when they have money, and they are hooked to ordering particular foods and things online because of the convenience provided by online shops and courier services.

According to Jiang et. al (2013) Online consumers have the advantage of shopping at any time and are able to make multiple economies of time. They can also purchase products from such locations as home and office, rather than at physical stores. In addition Jiang et. al (2013) also stated that online shopping convenience positively correlates with behavioral intentions. Specifically, the more convenience that is perceived on searching, transaction and possession/post-purchase, the greater is the possibility for repurchasing and recommendation by the customer

1.4 Monthly parcel

Table 4 shows the Monthly parcel profile of the **respondents** in terms of the **Monthly parcel**

Monthly parcel	Frequency	Percentage
5 pcs and below	120	66%
6 pcs to 10 pcs	52	26%
11 pcs to 20 pcs	24	4%
More than 20pcs	24	4%
Total	220	100%

Table 4 demonstrates that more consumers are purchasing bundles of less than 5 pieces which is 66% of the respondents. It means that, as a result of the epidemic, most individuals have run out of big amounts of money, or that consumer income has plummeted, and they are only purchasing essentials or necessities. Due to the epidemic, the majority of respondents claimed that they buy their wants on occasion and only buy stuffs that are essentially for them.

An article entitled “Impact of Coronavirus (COVID-19) on Consumer Behavior in 2020 (2021)” stated that Impact on shopping behavior ramped up alongside the pandemic itself in early March. When Numerator began fielding our survey the week of March 10, only 1 in 3 consumers claimed their shopping behavior had been impacted by the emerging COVID-19 pandemic

2. Assessing the Courier’s Company distribution problem using SERVQUAL Model.

2.1 Reliability

Table 5 shows the SERVQUAL Model of Courier’s Company distribution problem in terms of reliability.

Table 5. Reliability

Reliability	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Description
The courier's billing is accurate.	3.55	2	Strongly Agree
The courier ensures that my records are correct.	3.64	1	Strongly Agree
The courier performs the service at the designated time.	3.4	3	Agree
Reliability	3.53		Strongly Agree

The researchers discovered that “The courier ensures that my records are correct.” are an important factor to remember Courier’s Company distribution problem, with a weighted mean of **3.64** and a verbal definition of **strongly agree**. On the other hand, the researchers also discovered that “The courier performs the service at the designated time.” which received of the lowest weighted mean of **3.4** with verbal description of **agree**.

Based on the data in the table above, it is clear that the vast majority of respondents' records are correct, and the courier service performed an excellent job of ensuring, that this is a reason for consumers to select or choose their courier service again in the near future. According to the majority of respondents, keeping records is important since it allows them to examine previous transactions they have performed, as well as knowing the date and time of the transaction.

According to an article entitled “Collecting and storing customer information (2021)” Collecting and storing information about customers is essential to tailoring your customer service program and growing your business. It's good business practice to record the details of any customer enquiries so you can follow them up. Enquiries also give you an opportunity to collect customer information and mention your website, mailing list or social media pages

2.2 Responsiveness

Table 6 shows the SERVQUAL Model of Courier’s Company distribution problem in terms of responsiveness.

Table 6. Responsiveness

Responsiveness	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Description
As soon as possible, the courier sends me a transaction slip.	3.29	1	Agree
The courier calls me back as soon as possible.	3.26	3	Agree
I get prompt service from the courier (e.g., setting up appointment quickly).	3.29	2	Agree
Responsiveness	3.28		Strongly Agree

The researchers discovered that “As soon as possible, the courier sends me a transaction slip.” are an important factor to remember Courier’s Company distribution problem, with a weighted mean of **3.29** and a verbal definition of **Agree**. On the other hand, the researchers also discovered that “The courier calls me back as soon as possible.” which received of the lowest weighted mean of **3.26** with verbal description of **agree**

Based on the results above and the verbal explanation of **agree**, It indicates that the majority of respondents believe that providing a transaction slip is highly important to them when it comes to responsiveness. Transaction slips may contain information that is required when there are problems with an item or items received by customers. According to the respondents, the transaction slip is a show of transparency for both them and the courier.

According to an article entitled “BEING TRANSPARENT WITH YOUR CUSTOMERS (2018)” transparency throughout the delivery process can improve overall customer satisfaction. Strategies to improve transparency include showing delivery prices and not having hidden extra costs at checkout, having the ability to track packages, and knowing when the delivery will be made, and where it has been left

2.3 Competence

Table 7 shows the SERVQUAL Model of Courier’s Company distribution problem in terms of competence.

Table 7. Competence

Competence	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Description
Contact personnel of the courier company are knowledgeable and skilled.	3.37	1	Agree
Operational support of the courier company are knowledgeable and skilled	3.26	3	Agree
The courier company possesses research abilities, such as brokerage capabilities.	3.29	2	Agree
Competence	3.31		Strongly Agree

The researchers discovered that “Contact personnel of the courier company are knowledgeable and skilled.” are an important factor to remember Courier’s Company distribution problem, with a weighted mean of **3.37** and a verbal definition of **Agree**. On the other hand, the researchers also discovered that “Operational support of the courier company are knowledgeable and skilled” which received of the lowest weighted mean of **3.26** with verbal description of **agree**.

According to the table above, with the highest weighted mean of 3.37 and verbal description of Agree, it shows how contact personnel's knowledge and skill are critical to a courier company, and having those traits may help the company in terms of treating and providing convenience to their consumers. According to the majority of respondents, when they are in contact with a personnel who possesses positive characteristics, they feel assured, assured in the sense that the personnel have all of the information that a customer should be aware of while also providing convenience.

According to an article entitled “The Benefits of Having a Skilled Workforce (2019)” Skilled workers are an asset for any business as they play a large role in developing a business’s reputation and ongoing success. Skilled workers are experts at their job, and this means improved productivity for your business. In addition, according to Ken Lloyd (2021) Your employees’ knowledge, expertise, and skills are central to success on the job, and they require specific attention in the performance-appraisal process. When appraising your employees in this area, you may be tempted to focus on the Your employees’ knowledge, expertise, and skills are central to success on the job, and they require specific attention in the performance-appraisal process. When appraising your employees in this area, you may be tempted to focus on the amount of information they’ve amassed, and then appraise them solely on this factor. of information they’ve amassed, and then appraise them solely on this factor.

2.4 Access

Table 8 shows the SERVQUAL Model of Courier’s Company distribution problem in terms of access.

Table 8. Access

Access	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Description
I can call courier service number in a quick response (callers never have to wait and can stay on the line).	3.09	4	Agree
I rarely have to wait for a long time when I need courier service.	3.18	3	Agree
The courier delivers at a time that is convenient for me.	3.43	2	Agree
The delivery service has convenient service facilities at its locations.	3.47	1	Agree
Access	3.29		Strongly Agree

The researchers discovered that “The delivery service has convenient service facilities at its locations.” are an important factor to remember Courier’s Company distribution problem, with a weighted mean of **3.47** and a verbal definition of **Agree**. On the other hand, the researchers also discovered I can call courier service number in a quick response (callers never have to wait and can stay on the line).” which received of the lowest weighted mean of **3.09** with verbal description of **agree**

According to the table above, The delivery service has convenient service facilities at its locations with a weighted mean of 3.47 and a verbal description of agree implies that giving them a convenient factor may lead to use their service again. Customers benefit from delivery services since they can readily acquire or obtain their items more quickly. According to the respondents, having a transaction point close to their location saves them time since they can acquire their order quickly and use their time for other things rather than wasting time traveling to a distant transaction point.

Ricou (2020) stated that pickup points offer many varieties to your customers, strengthening the reliability of your business. In addition, it shows that you are attentive to their needs and that you optimize the customer experience.

2.5 Courtesy

Table 9 shows the SERVQUAL Model of Courier’s Company distribution problem in terms of courtesy.

Table 9. Courtesy

Courtesy	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal description
Customers' property is respected by the couriers (e.g., muddy shoes are not allowed on the carpet).	2.93	2	Agree
The contact personnel have a clean and neat appearance in public.	3.05	1	Agree
Courtesy	2.99		Agree

The researchers discovered that “The contact personnel have a clean and neat appearance in public.” are an important factor to remember Courier’s Company distribution problem, with a weighted mean of **3.05** and a verbal definition of **Agree**. On the other hand, the researchers also discovered that “Customers' property is respected by the couriers (e.g., muddy shoes are not allowed on the carpet).” which received of the lowest weighted mean of **2.93** with verbal description of **agree**.

According to the data in the table above, the verbal description of Agree has the highest mean of 3.05. It means that customers place a high value on employees who present themselves in a clean and orderly manner. Any type or appearance of a company's employees represents the organization. This is crucial since it will determine whether or not the consumer would use the courier service again in the future. Most respondents mentioned that having a clean and neat appearance of a personnel is essential to them because they believe that if a personnel is not that clean and has a not-so-clean appearance, their order stuff may not be cared for since a personnel cannot care for himself or herself.

According to Faro (2011), Appearance plays a big part on the workplace not only in how your colleagues and management view you, but also how you view yourself. When you look good, you feel good and ultimately become more productive. The quality of your work might be the most important thing but your appearance also leaves an immediate impression on your colleagues, including management.

2.6 Communication

Table 10 shows the SERVQUAL Model of Courier’s Company distribution problem in terms of communication.

Table 10. Communication

Communication	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal description
The courier helps me by providing me information about the service.	2.71	4	Agree
The courier gave me information on the service's fee.	3.5	1	Strongly Agree
The couriers explain the trade-off between service and cost to me.	2.74	2	Agree
I trust that the courier will take care of any problems that arise.	2.73	3	Agree
Communication	2.92		Agree

The researchers discovered that “The courier gave me information on the service's fee.” are an important factor to remember Courier’s Company distribution problem, with a weighted mean of **3.5** and a verbal definition of **Strongly Agree**. On the other hand, the researchers also discovered that “The courier helps me by providing me information about the service.” which received of the lowest weighted mean of **2.71** with verbal description of **agree**.

As indicated by the highest mean of 3.5 and the verbal description of Strongly Agree in the table above, it shows that providing clients with information about the courier's service pricing is a critical component in connection with them. If the service charge information is provided, the client will be aware of any hidden fees, as well as the whole list of fees that the customer is expected to be aware of in order to operate in a transparent manner. According to the respondents, service charge information is crucial to them because they want to know how much the whole cost of services such as door-to-door delivery and other services that they provide.

Furthermore, if the company lacks transparency with its customers, they are more likely to use another courier company.

Weinhouse (2018) stated that customers want transparency. Businesses know this and many of them talk about the need to be more transparent with their customers. But when it comes to actually implementing transparency practices, many companies turn and run the other way. The idea of losing potential customers by giving them access to information that doesn't portray the company in the best possible light is just too scary.

2.7 Credibility

Table 11 shows the SERVQUAL Model of Courier's Company distribution problem in terms of credibility.

Table 11. Credibility

Credibility	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal description
I trust their courier service because I've seen their brand name.	3.37	1	Agree
I respect the courier's company because of their excellent reputation.	2.58	4	Agree
The personnel of the couriers are strong in terms of personal characteristics	2.93	3	Agree
The degree of hard sell involved in interactions with the customer.	3.08	2	Agree
Credibility	2.99		Agree

The researchers discovered that “The researchers discovered that “I trust their courier service because I've seen their brand name.” are an important factor to remember Courier's Company distribution problem, with a weighted mean of **3.37** and a verbal definition of **Agree**. On the other hand, the researchers also discovered that “I respect the courier's company because of their excellent reputation.” which received of the lowest weighted mean of **2.58** with verbal description of **agree**.

Given the data above, the highest weighted mean of 3.37 with verbal description of agree suggests that when customers see the brand name of a courier service, they are more likely to trust the service provider. Having a courier service or any business that potential clients can trust when they see their brand is important since it indicates that a company in this type of situation may be at a vital point in terms of gaining or benefiting more frequently. Respondents feel more confident when they see their favorite courier service because they know their ordered things or food are in good hands.

According to a blog titled “6 reasons why a strong brand is important for your small business (2021)” a brand represents the sum of people's perception of a company's customer service, reputation, advertising and logo. And when all of these parts of the business are working well together, the overall brand tends to be healthy.

2.8 Security

Table 12 shows the SERVQUAL Model of Courier's Company distribution problem in terms of security.

Table 12. Security

Security	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal description
Physical security is provided by the courier.	3.05	3	Agree
Financial security is provided by the courier.	3.32	2	Agree
Our transactions with the courier company are conducted in a private and confidential manner.	3.56	1	Strongly Agree
Security	3.31		Strongly Agree

The researchers discovered that “Our transactions with the courier company are conducted in a private and confidential manner.” are an important factor to remember Courier's Company distribution problem, with a

weighted mean of **3.56** and a verbal definition of **Strongly Agree**. On the other hand, the researchers also discovered that “Physical security is provided by the courier” which received of the lowest weighted mean of **3.05** with verbal description of **agree**.

Based on the data in the table above, the highest mean of 3.56 combined with a verbal explanation of strongly agree implies that the courier service is doing a great job of providing their clients with private and secret transactions. It is critical because the respondents may feel secure in every transaction that he or she conducts, and because the respondents only know what he or she has ordered and when it will be delivered, it aids in the prevention of scammers operating online. According to the majority of respondents, a private and confidential transaction is crucial to them since it protects them from online scammers who tell them they need to pay again or result to them not receiving their ordered items or food.

According to Parker (2017), stated that customer confidentiality means keeping information about people who use your products and services private. When a customer patronizes a business, he may have to give information such as his name, address or financial accounts. Certain services or products may also be embarrassing for a customer to admit he uses. Keeping customer records confidential establishes trust between the business and the client. Certain types of customer information should always be protected, especially social security numbers and credit or checking account numbers.

2.9 Understanding/Knowing the customer

Table 13 shows the SERVQUAL Model of Courier’s Company distribution problem in terms of Understanding/Knowing the customer.

Table 13. Understanding/ Knowing The Customer

Understanding/Knowing The customer	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal description
The courier instructed me on the following specific requirements	2.5	3	Agree
Individualized attention is provided by the courier.	2.6	2	Agree
Regular customers are recognized by the courier.	3.09	1	Agree
Understanding/Knowing The customer	2.73		Agree

The researchers discovered that “Regular customers are recognized by the courier.” are an important factor to remember Courier’s Company distribution problem, with a weighted mean of **3.09** and a verbal definition of **Agree**. On the other hand, the researchers also discovered that “The courier instructed me on the following specific requirements” which received of the lowest weighted mean of **2.5** with verbal description of **agree**.

The table shows above the highest mean of 3.09 with verbal description of agree shows that a courier service or a company has a solid understanding of its clients because they are familiar with their regular customers It is possible that by placing greater emphasis on a regular customer, the firm will be able to attract new clients with the support of the regular customer who will recommend the company to their friends and family. According to the majority of respondents, when a courier knows them well, it provides them with greater happiness by making them feel important to the courier service as well.

According to an article entitled “ The Importance of Customer Recognition (2020)” Providing your customers with proper recognition can help you retain loyal customers as your business grows. Learn more about the importance of recognizing your customers and showing your appreciation wen running a business. Additionally, when you show your appreciation, customers are more likely to think of you the next time they need one of your products or services. Over time, this can grow into customer loyalty, which can help you achieve your sales goals.

2.10 Tangibles

Table 14 shows the SERVQUAL Model of Courier’s Company distribution problem in terms of tangibles.

Table 14. Tangibles

Tangibles	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal description
I don't have any issues with the courier's facilities.	2.61	4	Agree
I don't have any issues with the courier's personnel appearance.	3.17	2	Agree
I am confident with the couriers' tools or equipment utilized to offer the service.	3.36	1	Agree
I don't have any issues with the courier's physical representation of service (eg. Parcel packaging)	2.89	3	Agree
Tangibles	3.00		Strongly Agree

The researchers discovered that “I am confident with the couriers' tools or equipment utilized to offer the service.” are an important factor to remember Courier’s Company distribution problem, with a weighted mean of **3.36** and a verbal definition of **Agree**. On the other hand, the researchers also discovered that “I don't have any issues with the courier's facilities.” which received of the lowest weighted mean of **2.61** with verbal description of **agree**.

The highest weighted mean of 3.36 with a verbal description of agree suggests that the respondents had faith in the courier tools and equipment, which is consistent with the findings above. These tools and equipment may help to secure the food and other items that customers have requested, and from there, it may be possible to deliver the item safely, resulting in customer satisfaction. According to the majority of respondents, they have faith in the courier service's tools and equipment since they know they are receiving their food and other products in a safe and secure manner. They also believe that the courier service's vehicles are of good quality and dependability.

According to an article entitled “ The Benefits of Equipping Your Employees With the Right Tools (2017)” When your employees don’t have the tools they need, it forces them to get creative and use what they have to the best of their ability. This can greatly hurt productivity in your workplace, which can also hurt your organization’s bottom line. When you provide your employees with the proper tools, on the other hand, they don’t have to get creative and it allows them to focus on getting the job done as efficiently as possible rather than on how to get the job done with the wrong tool.

3. Proposed Client Action Plan for the Customer Service Companies

The researchers used the data gathered in formulating a client action plant as reference for the Customer Service Companies.

Table 15 is the proposed action client plan for the customer service companies. It contains different columns that are related from one another.

Table 13. Proposed Action Plan

CUSTOMERS' PROBLEMS	SOLUTION	OBJECTIVE OF THE SOLUTION	IMPLEMENTING STRATEGIES	PERSON RESPONSIBLE	REVIEW	IMPLEMENTATION
The courier performs the service at the designated time.	Provide series of leadership trainings, workshops, and teambuilding activities. Involvement in meetings.	To strengthen employee bonds and keep them productive, resulting in excellent job performance and the elimination of difficulties such as failure to provide service on time.	This activity will include numerous principles and models of what makes a good employee, such as qualities, attitude, skills, and other aspects of becoming a good employee. This method will assist in visualizing the whole image of the firm.	Supervisory level and Higher position.	Present the solution to supervisory level employee or higher position Ask their comments for revisions	Set the goals and explaining the objective to the employees that are included Determining the Roles, Responsibilities and Relationship Delegate the Work Execute the Plan, Monitor Progress and Performance, and Provide Continued Support
Operational support of the courier company are not that knowledgeable and skilled	Provide seminars and workshops	To enable the courier's operational assistance to be more advanced, skilled, and knowledgeable in order to do their work well.	This activity will include a conversation and instruction to the operational support person on how to be more dependable to customers.	Supervisor, Manager and Human Resource employee	Present the solution to the problem to the supervisor, manager, and human resource personnel. Inquire about their go signal and any feedback they have to help improving or enhance the solution.	Defining the seminar's objectives Define the employees who must attend the seminar. Choosing the best date based on the availability of attendees Locating an appropriate location Organize Your Activities Communication
The courier do not instructed me on the following specific requirements	Provide meeting and training to the employees	To assess the problem to them and knowing the assigned employee side why there's a neglecting to their job	This activity will know the reason of neglecting the job of the employee and giving them proper training and discussion to be more reliable to the customers	Supervisor, Manager	Present the solution to supervisor and manager Ask for their insights	Assess training needs Set organizational training objectives Create training action plan Implement training initiatives Evaluate & revise training
The courier do not provide a	Provide seminars and workshops	To teach them proper manners when handling a customer	This activity focuses on dealing with customers in a professional manner in order to be dependable and productive.	Supervisor, Human Resource employee	Presents the solution and ask their opinion to enhanced the solution	Defining the seminar's objectives Define the employees who must attend the seminar.

						Choosing the best date based on the availability of attendees Locating an appropriate location Organize Your Activities Communication
Physical security is not provided by the courier	Hire new staff; Provides seminar to Human Resource Employee and Manager	To achieve the steady growth of the business operation	This strategy will provide additional benefit in the security department of the company by adding new person who will deal with the production process of the business.	Top level Employee to Manager and Human Resource	Presents the solution and ask their opinion to enhanced the solution	Identify the hiring need Devise A Recruitment Plan Write a job description Advertise the Position Recruit the Position Review Applications Phone Interview/Initial Screening Interviews

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The majority of those who took part in this study were women between the ages of 18 and 30 with monthly incomes of less than 5,000 pesos. Despite having a low monthly income, the majority of respondents were tempted to buy their wants on occasion and focused on purchasing necessities due to covid 19.

When replying to the SERVQUAL Assessment of the courier services in reliability, the respondents "agree" that the courier ensures their record is correct so they can analyze prior transactions they have conducted. In terms of response, the courier sends a transaction slip that is critical to both the courier and the customer. Section of Competence and Courtesy, the personnel of the courier services have a clean and neat appearance, as agreed by the respondents, and having those appearances may affect the image of the company, In addition, knowledgeable and being skillful by the employees brings convenience to the consumers. Respondents feel more at ease with courier services because of the close proximity of pick-up places. For the communication, the courier provided information about a transaction slip cost in order to tell consumers about their total fee and to be upfront with them. In terms of credibility, the courier's brand name may inspire trust when people see it, as well as due to the courier's excellent performance. In Security, the courier firm conducts the transaction with the client quietly and confidentially to avoid problems with it and being agreed upon by the consumers. Understanding the clients, the courier acknowledges the regular customers frequently in order to establish confidence and have the regular customers recommend the company to their friends and family. Finally, tangibles, tools, and equipment are critical to providing excellent service to the consumer, which is why the courier service transports the foods and items purchased by the responders safely.

It is recommended to use different interventions which are applicable in solving the problems encountered by the respondents on their business. It may help them in identifying their efficiency gains and cost savings.

Strengthening the use of giving importance to regular customer of the Courier serviced and adopt other best practices to replace the ineffectual practices By doing so, the Courier services may achieve longevity and profitability in their own field of industry and may enhance their business

Strengthening the other factors that results to have possible customers and make a plan in able to sustain the business based on SERVQUAL MODEL will lead in the new strategic direction and digital transformation of the respondents which may result to the enhancement of the quality of their products and services to gain profitability stabilization

It is recommended that the client action plan crafted by the researchers be used to help the respondents to gain more income even if they change their industry, and the ventures stated in the proposed development plan may augment their income and may expand, grow, and help the economy in the long run.

REFERENCES

- i. *6 reasons why a strong brand is important for your small business (2021)* Retrieved from <https://www.deluxe.com/blog/six-reasons-why-strong-brand-important-small-business/> Date Accessed on October 3, 2021
- ii. *Badruldin, B., Mohamed, Z., Sharifuddin, J., Rezai, G., Abdullah, A. M., Abd Latif, I., & Mohayidin, M. G. (2012). Clients' perception towards JAKIM service quality in Halal certification. Journal of Islamic Marketing.* Retrieved from https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=tl&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Badruldin%2C+Mohamed%2C+Sharifuddin%2C+Rezai%2C+Abdullah%2C++Latif+and+Mohayidin.+%282012%29%2C+%E2%80%9CClients%27+perception++towards+JAKIM+service+quality&btnG=#d=gs_qabs&u=%23p%3D7NC5X MEEj3kJ Date Accessed on October 1, 2021
- iii. *Brink, A., & Berndt, A. (2009). Relationship marketing and customer relationship management: Juta and Company Ltd.* Retrieved from https://books.google.de/books/about/Relationship_Marketing_and_Customer_Relation.html?id=4bCVObO6xDS&redir_esc=y Date Accessed on October 1, 2021
- iv. *Collecting and storing customer information (2021).* Retrieved from <https://www.business.qld.gov.au/running-business/consumer-laws/customer-service/customer-information> Date Accessed on October 3, 2021
- v. *Cooper Smith (2015). Gen X and baby boomers present a huge opportunity for online retailers.* Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.businessinsider.com/the-age-demographics-of-who-shops-online-and-on-mobile-2015-4%3famp> Date Accessed on October 3, 2021
- vi. *Diaz, Rowell (2019) Quality of Service of Selected Courier Service Company in Cabanatuan City: It's Implication to Customer Satisfaction,* Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333809480_Quality_of_Service_of_Selected_Courier_Service_Company_in_Cabanatuan_City_It's_Implication_to_Customer_Satisfaction Date Accessed on October 1, 2021
- vii. *Edmunds, R., Thorpe, M., & Conole, G. (2012). Student attitudes towards and use of ICT in course study, work and social activity: A technology acceptance model approach. British journal of educational technology, 43(1), 71-84.* Retrieved from https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=tl&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Edmunds%2C%09R.%2C%09Thorpe%2C%09M.%2C%09%26%09Conole%2C%09G.%09%282010%29.%09Student%09attitudes%09towards%09and%09use%09of%09ICT%09in%09course%09study%2C%09work%09and%09+social%09activity%3A%09A%09technology%09acceptance%09model%09approach%2C%09British%09Journal%09of%09Educational%09Technology.%0943%281%29%2C%0971-84.&btnG=#d=gs_qabs&u=%23p%3DHnboTThj8rsJ Date Accessed on October 3, 2021
- viii. *Escarment (2017). 6 BENEFITS OF USING COURIER SERVICES.* Retrieved from <https://www.escarpmentfund.ca/6-benefits-of-using-courier-services/> Date Accessed on October 3, 2021

- ix. Ghoumrassi, A., & Tigu, G. (2019). *The impact of the logistics management in customer satisfaction*. LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing. Retrieved from https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=tl&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=+Ghoumrassi%2C+Amine+%26+Tigu%2C+Gabriela.+%282017%29.+The+impact+of+logistics+management+in+customer++satisfaction.+Proceedings+of+the+International+Conference+on+Business+Excellence.+11.+10.1515%2Fpicbe-2017-0031&btnG=#d=gs_qabs&u=%23p%3DFrzAimY6DJcJ Date Accessed on October 1, 2021
- x. Hong, W., Zheng, C., Wu, L., & Pu, X. (2019). *Analyzing the relationship between consumer satisfaction and fresh e-commerce logistics service using text mining techniques*. *Sustainability*, 11(13), 3570. Retrieved from https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=tl&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=+Hong%2C+Wei+%26+Zheng%2C+Changyuan+%26+Wu%2C+Linhai+%26+Pu%2C+Xujin.+%282019%29.+Analyzing+the+Relationship++between+Consumer+Satisfaction+and+Fresh+E-Commerce+Logistics+Service+Using+Text+Mining++Techniques.+Sustainability.+11.+3570.+10.3390%2Fsu11133570.&btnG=#d=gs_qabs&u=%23p%3DltCnlyyHZKoJ Date Accessed on October 1, 2021
- xi. Jamal, H. Z., Mahamed Ali, F., & Azmi, R. (2018). *The relationships between service quality and customer satisfaction of a courier service provider: towards more focus approach*. *Academic Journal of Business and Social Sciences* (g), 2, 1-13. Retrieved from <https://ir.uitm.edu.my/id/eprint/29994/> Date Accessed on October 1, 2021
- xii. Jiang, L. A., Yang, Z., & Jun, M. (2013). *Measuring consumer perceptions of online shopping convenience*. *Journal of Service management*. Retrieved from https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=tl&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Measuring+consumer+perceptions+of+online+shopping+convenience&btnG=#d=gs_qabs&u=%23p%3DlS6ZhuEu79MJ Date Accessed on October 3, 2021
- xiii. Johnson, E. H. I. G. I. E., & Karley, J. (2018). *Impact of service quality on customer satisfaction*. Retrieved from <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A1246475&dswid=8401> Date Accessed on October 2, 2021
- xiv. Ken Lloyd (2021). *Employee Appraisal Phrases: Job Knowledge and Expertise*. Retrieved from <https://www.dummies.com/business/human-resources/employee-relations/employee-appraisal-phrases-job-knowledge-and-expertise/> Date Accessed on October 3, 2021
- xv. Khan, M. M., & Fasih, M. (2014). *Impact of service quality on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty: Evidence from banking sector*. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences (PJCSS)*, 8(2), 331-354. Retrieved from <https://www.econstor.eu/handle/10419/188141> Date Accessed on October 2, 2021
- xvi. Manon Ricou (2020). *Pickup Points: what benefits for your E-commerce?* Retrieved from <https://www.blog.shippypro.com/advantages-drop-off-points-for-ecommerce/> Date Accessed on October 3, 2021
- xvii. Michael Weinhouse (2018). *Why You Should Be Radically Transparent With Your Customers* Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.forbes.com/sites/forbesagencycouncil/2018/04/16/why-you-should-be-radically-transparent-with-your-customers/amp/> Date Accessed on October 3, 2021
- xviii. Naidoo, V. (2011, October). *Managerial Issues Associated with Service Quality-The Case of the University of Kwa-Zulu-Natal*. In *ICBER 2011 Conference*. Retrieved from https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=tl&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Naidoo%2C+V.+%282011%29.+Managerial+Issues+Associated+with+Service+Quality-The+Case+of++the+University+of+Kwa-Zulu-Natal.+In+ICBER+2011+Conference.&btnG=#d=gs_qabs&u=%23p%3Db23qW2i0NWgJ Date Accessed on October 2, 2021
- xix. Ok, S., Suy, R., Chhay, L., & Choun, C. (2018). *Customer satisfaction and service quality in the marketing practice: Study on literature review*. *Asian Themes in Social Sciences Research*, 1(1), 21-27.

- Retrieved from https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=tl&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Ok%2C+S.%2C+Suy%2C+R.%2C+Chhay%2C+L.%2C+%26+Choun%2C+C.+%282018%29.+Customer+Satisfaction+and+Service+Quality+in+the++Marketing+Practice%3A+Study+on+Literature+Review.+Asian+Themes+in+Social+Sciences+Research%2C+1%281%29%2C+&btnG=#d=gs_qabs&u=%23p%3DU3j-lA8hGpsJ Date Accessed on October 1, 2021
- xx. Owusu-Frimpong, N., & Nwankwo, S. (2012). Service quality orientation: an approach to diffusing mindfulness in SMEs. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*. Retrieved from https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=tl&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Owusu-Frimpong%2C+N.+and+Nwankwo%2C+S.+%282012%29%2C+%E2%80%9CService+quality+orientation%3A+an+approach+to+diffusing++mindfulness+in+SMEs%E2%80%9D%2C+International+Journal+of++Quality+%26+Reliability+Management%2C+29%286%29%3A681-698.&btnG=#d=gs_qabs&u=%23p%3DqWFWCpgcHbgJ Date Accessed on October 1, 2021
- xxi. Parasuraman, A Parsu & Zeithaml, Valarie & Berry, Leonard. (1985). A Conceptual Model of Service Quality and its Implication for Future Research (SERVQUAL). *The Journal of Marketing*. 49. 41-50. 10.2307/1251430. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/225083670_A_Conceptual_Model_of_Service_Quality_and_its_Implication_for_Future_Research_SERVQUAL Date accessed November 6, 2021
- xxii. Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, L. (1988). SERVQUAL: A multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality. 1988, 64(1), 12-40. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/225083802_SERVQUAL_A_multiple-Item_Scale_for_measuring_consumer_perceptions_of_service_quality Date Accessed on October 1, 2021
- xxiii. Pena, M. M., Silva, E. M. S. D., Tronchin, D. M. R., & Melleiro, M. M. (2013). The use of the quality model of Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry in health services. *Revista da Escola de Enfermagem da USP*, 47(5), 1227-1232. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0080-623420130000500030> Date Accessed on October 1, 2021
- xxiv. Raosoft, I. (2011). Sample Size Calculator. Sample Size Calculator link - <http://www.raosoft.com/samplesize.html> Date Accessed on October 3, 2021
- xxv. Saliba, K., & Zoran, A. G. (2018). Measuring higher education services using the SERVQUAL model. *Journal of Universal Excellence*, 4, 160-179. Retrieved from https://scholar.google.com/scholar?start=40&q=Servqual+model&hl=tl&as_sdt=0,5&as_ylo=2017#d=gs_qabs&u=%23p%3DOYYBTOJ-4ygJ Date Accessed on October 1, 2021
- xxvi. Sureshchandar, G. S., Rajendran, C., & Anantharaman, R. N. (2002). The relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction—a factor specific approach. *Journal of services marketing*, 16(4), 363-379. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/235299219_The_relationship_between_service_quality_and_customer_satisfaction-a_factor_specific_approach Date Accessed on October 2, 2021
- xxvii. Terrique Faro (2021). How Important is Appearance in the Workplace? Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.skillsportal.co.za/content/how-important-appearance-workplace%3famp> Date Accessed on October 3, 2021
- xxviii. The Benefits of Equipping Your Employees With the Right Tools (2017). Retrieved from <https://www.safecutters.com/blog/the-benefits-of-equipping-your-employees-with-the-right-tools/> Date Accessed on October 3, 2021
- xxix. The Benefits of Having a Skilled Workforce (2019) Retrieved from <https://www.advancedgroupservices.com.au/the-benefits-of-having-a-skilled-workforce/> Date Accessed on October 3, 2021
- xxx. The Importance of Customer Recognition by The Siliconreview (2020). Retrieved from <https://thesiliconreview.com/2020/09/the-importance-of-customer->

